

VIDZEME UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES
ENGINEERING FACULTY

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**AN EASY COMMUNICATION
IMPLEMENTATION OF HETEROGENEOUS
AND DISTRIBUTED SIMULATION MODELS**

SUMMARY OF THE DOCTORAL THESIS

Thematically united set of scientific publications

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I hereby confirm having written this doctoral thesis which I have submitted to Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences for obtaining a doctoral degree (Ph.D). The doctoral thesis has not been submitted to any other university.

Artis Aizstrauts

Datums:

Doctoral thesis is a set of thematically united set of scientific publications. Doctoral thesis contains a summary and 13 scientific publications, accessible via Annex B. The publications are 128 pages long and written in English.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABM	–	<i>Agent Based Model</i>
ALSP	–	<i>Aggregate Level Simulation Protocol</i>
AMQP	–	<i>Advanced Message Queuing Protocol</i>
API	–	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
CLD	–	<i>Causal Loop Diagram</i>
CORBA	–	<i>Common Object Request Broker Architecture</i>
DDS	–	<i>Data-Distribution Service for Real-Time Systems</i>
DIS	–	<i>Distributed Interactive Simulation</i>
EC2	–	<i>Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud</i>
ECE	–	<i>Easy Communication Environment</i>
FIPA	–	<i>The Foundation for Physical Intelligent Agents</i>
FOM	–	<i>Federation Object Model</i>
HLA	–	<i>High Level Architecture</i>
HTTP	–	<i>Hypertext Transfer Protocol</i>
IoT	–	<i>Internet of Things</i>
ISO OSI 7498	–	<i>International Organization for Standardization Open Systems Interconnection 7498 standard</i>
JSON	–	<i>JavaScript Object Notation</i>
LCM	–	<i>Lightweight Communications and Marshalling</i>
MI	–	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
MQTT	–	<i>Message Queue Telemetry Transport</i>
ORB	–	<i>Object Request Broker</i>
QoS	–	<i>Quality of Service</i>
ROS	–	<i>Robot Operating System</i>
SOA	–	<i>Service Oriented Architecture</i>

1. OVERVIEW OF THE THESIS

1.1. Scientific field and subfield

The promotion thesis refers to scientific field “Electrical engineering, electronics, information and communication technologies”, and to corresponding subfield “System analysis, modelling and design”.

1.2. Practical significance

Digital technologies have become the cornerstone of our society and economy. The quality of these technologies determines our well-being and living conditions. Digital transformation affects people's everyday life, individual behaviour and way of communication. Likewise, technologies change production, public administration, agriculture, education, etc. sectors and decision-making within them. Thorough impact continues from penetration of artificial intelligence (AI) and development of Big Data analytics, cloud computing, mobile technologies, business intelligence and Internet of Things (IoT) (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Digital technology market is expanding at a remarkable speed and volume. The size of the global digital transformation market in 2023 was \$880.28 billion but is expected to reach \$1,070.43 billion in 2024. The market growth is characterized by a compound annual growth rate of about 27.6%. Projections suggest that the size of the digital transformation market will reach \$4,617.78 billion by 2030 (Grand View Research, 2024).

Today's society can be characterised as a sociotechnical system, the sustainability of which is dependent upon the advancement of digital technologies' sustainability. The stochastic nature of digital technology, which includes a hidden set of influences (Ginters and Revathy, 2021), as well as a pervasive nature, has the most diverse and unexpected impacts on the development of society, the economy, and the environment, as well as on the daily life of everyone.

The relevance of data collection, processing, analysis, and contextualization technologies in decision-making grows along with their variety. Many organizations rely heavily on data-driven decisions and well-founded projections to run their operations. As a result, the need for well-founded and data-driven forecasts and decisions is increasing. Simulation modelling is useful as a method for developing reliable forecasts and validating the development of various scenarios.

The model of a sociotechnical system is a simplified representation of objective reality, yet it, nevertheless, retains complexity due to the large number of stochastic influencing elements. Complex problems cannot be explained by primitive and/or homogeneous patterns. The model of a real sociotechnical system is heterogeneous, and that likely means using various simulation modelling techniques. Queue and delay-related processes can be modelled using discrete-event simulation, but agent-based models (ABM) are preferable for analysing the behaviour and interactions of individual objects, but the overall changes will be better specified by system dynamics simulation equations. In addition, if the model includes also data processing and analysis components, a heterogeneous and distributed modelling system is inevitable (Aizstrauts un Ginters, 2024).

In 2012, when conducting an analysis of distributed simulation platforms and tools, the author (Aizstrauts et al., 2012) found that the number of options is very limited with DIS (Distributed Interactive Simulation), HLA (High Level Architecture), CORBA (Common Object Request Broker Architecture), or customizable web service-based solutions. There were no universal and easy to use tools for designing distributed simulation models.

Nothing has fundamentally changed until today. Several sufficiently fast communication tools have emerged – ROS (Robot Operating System) and LCM (Lightweight Communications and Marshalling). However, they were created for real-time robotics applications, and the situation has forced modelers to use those to somehow compensate the lack of tools needed to design distributed models (Xu et al., 2021). The growth of IoT has contributed to the development of special device-device communication tools such as IoTivity (Xu et al., 2021). However, these tools provide heterogeneous model communication rather poorly. A ray of hope was the protocol and standard DDS (Data-Distribution Service for Real-Time Systems) (OMG, 2015) created by Object Management Group for real-time distributed operational systems. But these remained merely instructions and guidelines for achieving model interoperability and were never turned into actionable solutions (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

It must be acknowledged that the dominant tool to ensure the interaction of simulation models is the High Level Architecture (HLA), which was created by the US Department of Defence back in 1995 (Dahmann, Fujimoto and Weatherly, 1997), but it is also supplemented, improved and widely used in the civilian sector (Jabbour, Possik and Zacharewicz, 2023; Possik, 2021). In fact, HLA has become the industry standard for providing distributed models interoperability. One of the main drawbacks of HLA was and still is the fact that "*standard is*

too "heavy", i.e. very complex, difficult to learn and thus time consuming to adopt and use" (Strassburger, Schulze and Fujimoto, 2008), and without advanced skills in software engineering it is impossible to use HLA.

Thus, the solutions available to professionals in other fields to create a distributed simulation model without involving programming are rather limited. Enlisting qualified programming engineers will increase the financial costs of the project and complicate the administrative procedures. Moreover, the licensing terms of commercial tools will impose an additional financial burden on further distribution of the designed model (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Alternatively, simulation suite developers can incorporate multiple simulation technologies in one product that allows to construct heterogeneous models and has internal communication mechanisms, for example, AnyLogic (Borshchev, 2014). However, the question remains how to integrate already created models from other simulation environments, such as FlexSim (Wang, Wang and Zhang, 2022), NetLogo (Wilensky and Rand, 2015), etc., as well as provide a link to the subsystems of data analysis.

There is an urgent need for a tool that would enable modelers to make the previously impossible possible, and to allow industry professionals with basic knowledge in information technology and modelling to create distributed heterogeneous simulation models themselves, without the involvement of software developers and additional financial expenses.

If the modeler works with ABM, then he has at least a minimal understanding of object-oriented programming. If the modeler uses discrete-event tools, then he has knowledge of statistical processing of data and understands probabilities. If the modeler develops system dynamics models, then he is familiar with differential equations. That is, he has enough knowledge to create a distributed and heterogeneous simulation model using Easy Communication Environment (ECE).

1.3. Subject and object of the study

The subject of the study – distributed simulation communication environments.

Object of the study – communication and data exchange mechanism.

1.4. Research question

Whether and how it is possible to adapt pre-existing distributed simulation or data processing communication environments, which would be suitable for modelers without special knowledge in programming engineering (compliance with level 6 of the professional qualification standard of Programming Engineer NACE 62.01 and above) to develop distributed and heterogeneous simulation models?

1.5. Hypothesis

Easy Communication Environment (ECE) is suitable and universal alternative for modelers without specific programming knowledge and skills and it can replace the use of high-level architecture (HLA) in distributed and heterogeneous simulation models that do not require increased security demands.

1.6. The aim and objectives of the thesis

The aim. To allow modelers lacking programming engineering background to create distributed and heterogeneous simulation models, based on conceptual framework of open and easy communication environment.

To achieve this, the author defined several **objectives**:

1. To compare current simulation and data processing communication tools and assess their suitability for modelers outside of the software engineering field.
2. Develop open and easy conceptual framework that enables modelers without specific prior software engineering knowledge to create distributed and heterogeneous simulation models.
3. Test and validate Easy Communication Environment for distributed and heterogeneous models within different settings.

1.7. Scientific innovation

Open multi-layer ECE framework enables communication between heterogeneous simulation models, allowing modelers without specific programming skills to design and model various scenarios of sociotechnical systems development.

Advantages. With the help of ECE, modelers without specific software engineering skills can design distributed and heterogeneous simulation models and connect them with data processing systems. The current alternative is to rely solely on closed simulation modelling environment, without using previously created heterogeneous models.

Limitations. ECE uses *Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)*, but does not utilize the delivery acknowledgement, therefore the technology is not recommended for applications with increased security requirements.

1.8. Main statements

The results of the research support the following statements:

1. Existing distributed simulation communication environments are not suitable for modelers without specific software engineering skills, which limits the range of potential applications of distributed and heterogenous simulation models, and negatively impacts the decision-making process and quality.
2. The conceptual Framework of ECE enables modelers without specific software engineering skills to create heterogeneous and distributed simulation models for various use.
3. The framework of ECE is open and therefore provides easy implementation not only for simulation, but also for distributed data processing systems.

1.9. Structure and scope of the thesis

The doctoral thesis is a thematically united set of scientific publications, that consists of a summary and the whole set of author's scientific publications that were an integral part of ECE development process.

The first section serves as an introduction and is an overview of the thesis. The second section, in turn, contains information on the approbation of the findings within several scientific projects, in national and international conferences, and a list of corresponding publications. The third section focuses on the results of the research, particularly over ECE development steps, structural architecture and functionality, as well as examples of ECE application. It also discusses the suitability of ECE for modelling various cases. The final section is author's conclusions and list of references used for the summary. The thesis has two annexes – a BPMN2 functionality diagram, and copies of respective publications.

2. APPROBATION AND PUBLICATIONS

2.1. Research projects

Versions of ECE for distributed and heterogeneous simulation models have been tested in diverse applications and various national and international projects.

1. Nr. 2006/11 “Simulation Tools EXTEND and NetLogo use for Ecosystems Analysis” (Financed by Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Latvia).
2. Nr. 2007/1-17/26 “Communication Environment of Hybrid Simulation Systems” (Financed by Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Latvia).
3. No.2DP/2.1.1.2.0/10/APIA/VIAA/001 “Support for preparation of IST FP7 STRE project “Simulation Highway”” (Financed by European Regional Development Fund).
4. FP7 No.287119 FUPOL „Future Policy Modelling” (Financed by European Commission).
5. FP7 FLAG-ERA FuturICT 2.0 (2017-2020) "Large scale experiments and simulations for the second generation of FuturICT" (Financed by European Commission).

The research results were validated and used in the study course "Sociotechnical Systems Modelling" under the academic master programme “Cybersecurity engineering” (Riga Technical University), as well as within the professional master programme and doctoral programme “Sociotechnical Systems Modelling” (Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences).

2.2. Conferences

Scientific results on development of ECE have been reported in 16 conferences during 2006.-2024:

1. 6th WSEAS International Conference on Applied Computer Science (ACS'06), December 16-18, Puerto de la Cruz, Tenerife, Spain, 2006.
2. 3rd International Scientific Conference “Information Society and Modern Business”, September 21-22, Ventspils, Latvia, 2007.
3. 6th WSEAS International Conference on Systems Science and Simulation in Engineering, November 21-23, Venice, Italy, 2007.
4. 4th WSEAS/IASME International Conference on Educational Technologies (EDUTE'08), October 26-28, Corfu, Greece, 2008.
5. International Conference of Modelling and Simulation in Engineering, Economics and Management (MS'10), July 15-17, Barcelona, Spain, 2010.
6. 13th WSEAS International Conference on Automatic Control, Modelling & Simulation (ACMOS '11), May 27-29, Lanzarote, Canary Islands, Spain, 2011.

7. 23rd European Modelling & Simulation Symposium (EMSS 2011), September 12-14, Rome, Italy, 2011.
8. 5th WSEAS World Congress on Applied Computing Conference (ACC '12), May 2-4, Faro, Portugal, 2012.
9. CBU International Conference, April 4-17, Prague, Czech Republic, 2013.
10. 9th International Workshop on Enterprise and Organizational Modelling and Simulation (EOMAS 2013), June 17, Valencia, Spain, 2013.
11. 26th European Modelling & Simulation Symposium (EMSS 2014), September 10-12, Bordeaux, France, 2014.
12. World Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (WorldCIST'15), April 1-3, Ponta Delgada, São Miguel, Azores, Portugal, 2015.
13. 27th European Modelling & Simulation Symposium (EMSS 2015), September 21-23, Bergeggi, Italy, 2015.
14. City Planning and Urban Design Conference (CPUD'16), 07-09 April, Istanbul, 2016.
15. 61st International Scientific Conference on Information Technology and Management Science of Riga Technical University (ITMS'2020), October 15-16, Riga, Latvia, 2020.
16. 36th European Modelling & Simulation Symposium, September 18-20, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Spain, 2024.

2.3. Publications

Doctoral candidate Artis Aizstrauts (Scopus ID: 54413897200) has 30 scientific publications, 18 of which are indexed in Scopus (Artis Siliņš – 2, Artis Aizstrauts – 16). The following 13 publications, which share a common thematic focus, are included in this collection (see also Appendix B), and copies of these publications are attached. The most recent publication is an excerpt from the summary of the doctoral dissertation. Artis Aizstrauts' contribution to the publications is at least 90%, and the corresponding co-authors have no objections to this distribution, as confirmed by a separate statement. The total number of citations in Scopus is 140, and the Scopus h-index is 5 (October 2024).

1. Ginters, E., & Silins, A. (2007). Multi-level approach for environmental systems modelling in the Ligatne Natural Trails. *WSEAS Transactions on Systems*, 6(4), 795-801. Izgūts no https://www.researchgate.net/publication/297118169_Multi-level_approach_for_environmental_systems_modelling_in_the_Ligatne_Natural_Trails
2. Ginters, E., Silins, A., & Andrusaitis, J. (2007). Communication in Distributed Simulation Environment. In *ICOSSE'07: Proceedings of the 6th WSEAS international conference on System science and simulation in engineering* (pp. 217-221). Stevens

- Point: World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society. doi: 10.5555/1974442.1974475 Izgūts no <http://www.wseas.us/e-library/conferences/2007venice/papers/600-139.pdf>
3. Ginters, E., & Silins, A. (2008a). Exchange Mechanisms in Distributed Simulation of Sociotechnical Systems. In *Information Society and Modern Business. Proceedings of 3rd International conference, 21-22 September 2007, Ventspils* (p. 362). Ventspils: Ventspils University College. Izgūts no <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925129>
 4. Ginters, E., & Silins, A. (2008b). Simulation Data Exchange in Distributed E-learning Environment. In *Proceedings of the 4th WSEAS/IASME International Conference on Education Technologies (EDUTE'08)* (pp. 138-143). Corfu: WSEAS. Izgūts no <http://www.wseas.us/e-library/conferences/2008/corfu/edute/edute23.pdf>
 5. Silins, A., Ginters, E., & Aizstrauta, D. (2010). Easy Communication Environment for Distributed Simulation. In *Computational Intelligence in Business and Economics* (pp. 91-98). https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814324441_0014. Izgūts no https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282288675_Easy_Communication_Environment_for_Distributed_Simulation#fullTextFileContent
 6. Ginters, E., Sakne, I., Lauberte, I., Aizstrauts, A., Dreija, G., Aquilar China, R.-M., Merkurjev, Y., Novitsky, L., & Grundspenkis, J. (2011). Simulation Highway – Direct Access Intelligent Cloud Simulator. In *Proceedings of 23rd European Modelling & Simulation Symposium (EMSS 2011)* (pp. 62-72). Izgūts no <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925109>
 7. Aizstrauts, A., Ginters, E. & Aizstrauta, D. (2011). Easy Communication Approach for Data Exchange in Distributed Simulation Environment. In *Proceedings of the 13th WSEAS international conference on Automatic control, modelling & simulation (ACMOS'11)* (pp. 34-38). Stevens Point: World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society (WSEAS). Izgūts no <http://www.wseas.us/e-library/conferences/2011/Lanzarote/ACMOS/ACMOS-04.pdf>
 8. Aizstrauts, A., Ginters, E., Aizstrauta, D., & Sonntagbauer, P. (2012). Easy Communication Environment on the Cloud as Distributed Simulation Infrastructure. In *Proceedings of the 5th WSEAS congress on Applied Computing conference, and Proceedings of the 1st international conference on Biologically Inspired Computation (BICA'12)* (pp. 173-178). Stevens Point, Wisconsin: World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society (WSEAS). Izgūts no <http://www.wseas.us/e-library/conferences/2012/Algarve/BICA/BICA-29.pdf>
 9. Aizstrauts, A., Ginters, E., Lauberte, I., & Pjera Eroles, M.A. (2013). Multi-level Architecture on Web Services Based Policy Domain Use Cases Simulator. In *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing* (vol 153, pp.130-146). Berlin: Springer. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-41638-5_9. Izgūts no https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282289690_Multi-

level Architecture on Web Services Based Policy Domain Use Cases Simulator
#fullTextFileContent

10. Aizstrauts, A., Ginters, E., Baltruks, M., & Gusev, M. (2015). Architecture for Distributed Simulation Environment. *Procedia Computer Science*, 43, pp. 18-25. doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2014.12.004. Izgūts no <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050914015725>
11. Ginters, E., Aizstrauts, A., Baltruks, M., Merkuryev, Y., Novickis, L., Grundspenkis, J., & Grabis, J. (2016). VeloRouter - Technology for Urban Transport Intermodal Sustainability. In *City Planning and Urban Design Conference, 07-09 April (CPUD'16)* (pp. 211-220). Istanbul: DAKAM. ISBN 978-605-9207-21-8. Izgūts no <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925061>
12. Aizstrauts, A., Burkhardt, D., Ginters, E., & Nazemi, K. (2020). On Microservice Architecture Based Communication Environment for Cycling Map Developing and Maintenance Simulator. In *2020 61st International Scientific Conference on Information Technology and Management Science of Riga Technical University (ITMS)* (pp. 1-4). doi: 10.1109/ITMS51158.2020.9259299. Izgūts no https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347072223_On_Microservice_Architecture_Based_Communication_Environment_for_Cycling_Map_Developing_and_Maintenance_Simulator#fullTextFileContent
13. Aizstrauts, A. & Ginters, E. (2024). Easy Communication Environment for Heterogeneous and Distributed Simulation Models Design. In *2024 36th European Modeling & Simulation Symposium* (p. 1-13). Tenerife. doi: 10.46354/i3m.2024.emss.010. Izgūts no <https://www.caltek.eu/proceedings/i3m/2024/emss/010/pdf.pdf>

3. MAIN RESULTS

3.1. ECE development phases

Easy Communication Environment (ECE) development process (see the timeline in Figure 1) took more than 15 years, searching for the most effective and efficient solution, but also hoping for technology development that would enable communication between distributed and non-homogenous models.

In 2007, the author conducted research on Ligatne Natural Trails, which is part of the Gauja National Park in Latvia (Ginters and Silins, 2007). In a limited area, moose, deer, wild boar, wolves, bears, and other representatives of the national fauna live there in a natural environment. In order not to damage natural resources, the sightseeing places are connected by hiking trails.

Figure 1. ECE development timeline.

However, for the convenience of visitors, an asphalt road has been built, along which private cars can go in a certain route, with parking lots adjacent to each sight. The question of the research was, what is the acceptable load on the natural resource, so that visitor damage does not have irreversible implications and the resource is able to recover after a certain time interval?

It was necessary to create a discrete-event model that provides an analysis of the vehicle movement to determine the necessary amount of parking spaces, and what additional infrastructure needs to be built (WC, vending machines, waste collection bins, etc.). The model was implemented in the Extend Suite environment and served as a data source for the second

ABM model in the NetLogo environment, which assessed the regenerative capacity of the natural resource.

The key question for this work was, how to ensure the interoperability of models? A review of currently available distributed simulation support mechanisms was conducted. DIS and HLA were found to be usable. However, the implementation of an interoperability mechanism between the models in the HLA was laborious and complex. It became clear that designing distributed models using the tools HLA and similar is impossible without solid understanding of software engineering, and for nature researchers this path is closed.

The author continued looking for distributed simulation communication tools that would meet the requirements (Ginters, Silins and Andrusaitis, 2007).

In addition to HLA, the suitability of the Aggregate Level Simulation Protocol (ALSP), Common Object Request Broker Architecture (CORBA), and The Foundation for Physical Intelligent Agents (FIPA) was examined. Particular focus was placed on the CORBA mechanism, whose Object Request Broker (ORB) was used to ensure communication between Extend Suite and NetLogo models. Simulation environment's extension modules C++ (Extend Suite) and Java (NetLogo) were created. The solution enabled communication between the models, unfortunately it also required advanced programming skills (Aiztrauts and Ginters, 2024).

In 2008, the adaptation of the CORBA ORB mechanism for distributed simulation continued (Ginters and Silins, 2008a), however, issues due to poor CORBA performance, affected the modelling quality.

The author (Ginters and Silins, 2008b) turned to performance measurements and compared CORBA and HLA communication mechanisms. When the advantage of HLA over CORBA results rose considerably with message packet length, suspicions were confirmed. Since HLA's performance was seen as a crucial indicator, going with a slower solution would significantly limit the possibilities of implementing a communication tool in the future. It was decided that, under the parameters set forth, CORBA is not suitable for usage in distributed simulation models and further research of HLA potential was pursued.

In 2010, the author published a solution (Silins, Ginters and Aiztrauta, 2010) that eased access to the HLA federation. The solution was based on the Communication Adapter, which provided a link between the simulation model and HLA. The adapter was created as part of the HLA environment and interpreted the HLA data in a format that was understandable by the

simulation model. The communication adapter listened to the models and stored the sent messages in the data storage. Any other model that required the data could retrieve it from the data storage on demand. At the same time, data storage provided time synchronization options. Each simulation environment required a library to interact with the adapter. Cooperation between the simulation tool and adapter was initiated by requests in XML format. In conformity with the model parameters the adapter generated the Federation Object Model (FOM), which allowed to connect to the HLA federation. The adapter needed to be able to work with a variety of variables from various models, while also being simple to manage. The implementation of this requirement turned out to be more complicated than it seemed at first glance, as it provoked corresponding changes in the chain of compatibility with HLA. Thus, the first version of Easy Communication Environment (ECE) was born.

In 2011, the improvement of the first version of ECE continued, working on supplementing the simulation tools Communication library. An intermediate Communication Gateway was created that provided the data exchange among Communication Adapters prior to connection to the HLA environment (Aizstrauts, Ginters and Aizstrauta, 2011). The improvement reduced the modeler's workload by creating HLA-based distributed simulation models (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Since the first versions of the ECE were based on the presence of HLA, the search for more suitable communication environments, architectures, protocols, and message data formats continued (Ginters et al., 2011).

The author developed the Simulation Highway concept as a multi-layer open architecture, based on the principles of ISO OSI 7498 (International Organization for Standardization Open Systems Interconnection). In Simulation Highway, the execution of each modelling task was ensured by a chain of simulation elements. The requirements for specific programming skills decreased because for formulating the modelling queries high-level languages such as SimAL and SimQL could be used in accordance with the client-server approach. However, the basic mechanism of communication was still HLA. In addition, the implementation of Simulation Highway required significant data processing resources. After the self-assessment of the sustainability of Simulation Highway, this idea was abandoned (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

In 2012, the FP7 project No.287119 FUPOL was launched. In the framework of the project, several heterogeneous simulators were created – the planning & design of the zoning of a public park in Zagreb and forecasting of the occupancy of tourist facilities, and the planning of the

bicycle route network of the city of Skopje.

The FUPOL project was the next phase of ECE development (Aizstrauts et al., 2012), allowing previously developed ECE version to be validated. To implement and test response time boundary intervals in a territorially distributed model, the ECE was deployed in a virtual computing environment of Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2), while simulation model management was done with Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP). In this version of the ECE and in the future, the author abandoned the use of HLA, expanding the functionality of the previously designed Communication Gateway.

One of the main tasks of FUPOL project was to create a simulation-based support mechanism for policy decision-making. The consortium conducted an analysis of more than 60 generic and problem-oriented simulation tools, which confirmed earlier suspicions that most problem-oriented simulation environments are closed, and it is not possible to attach external models. Unfortunately, closed environments usually offer limited functionality that did not provide an implementation of heterogeneous distributed models.

The basic concept of the FUPOL simulator was developed (Aizstrauts et al., 2013), where Fuzzy Cognitive Maps and Coloured Petri Networks were used at the higher level of design, while simulation models were implemented in RePast Symphony. A system dynamics simulation environment STELLA was used to simulate system change over time. Data processing and analysis were implemented in Python and data was stored in PostgreSQL base. To improve the visualization of the results and facilitate the management of the modelling sessions, the NetLogo environment was used, because the visualization mechanism of the RePast Symphony was rather poor. Data exchange in FUPOL simulation subsystem was provided by the ECE. To ensure an interoperability with other FUPOL subsystems an ECE alignment with the Enterprise Service Bus was designed. To conclude, the FUPOL project provided an excellent validation opportunity for the ECE concept.

One of FUPOL's use cases where the ECE environment was validated was the Skopje Bicycle Route Simulator, also known as VeloRouter (Aizstrauts et al., 2015). Simulator was tasked to provide route choices for cyclists, depending on the load on the route, the quality of the pavement and infrastructure, as well as meteorological conditions. Here the ECE had to ensure interoperability between NetLogo, RePast and Python.

After carrying out an analysis of several Message Brokers, RabbitMQ was recognized as the most suitable and was subsequently used as an ECE component. The Advanced Message

Queuing Protocol (AMQP) was used by simulation model to communicate with the Message Broker.

Henceforth after the 2016 the author abandoned the use of any cloud-based services for communication needs, which did not provide a guaranteed response time and raised doubts about the timeline of the simulation session. The FUPOL validation results supplemented the ECE set of requirements, and specifically, not only the convenience of the modeler is important, but also the universality and security of the communication environment.

Afterwards ECE was validated in the process of creating the prototype of VeloRouter for the bicycle route planning (Aizstrauts et al., 2020). The research was initiated by previous FUPOL results and FP7 FLAG-ERA FuturICT 2.0 (2017-2020) project. VeloRouter users had the ability to develop their own routes, as well as recommend them to the municipality, providing feedback through ticketing, which is a basic rule for the development of sustainable management and control.

Here, for the first time, the multi-layer architecture of the ECE was presented and the functionality of each layer was defined. Based on the universality and compatibility requirement, the ECE communication and data exchange mechanism was based on JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) data formats and the AMQP protocol disclaiming further use of XML. The main requirement of ECE development was addressed – to provide opportunities for subject matter experts without specific software engineering skills to create and operate heterogeneous and distributed simulation models that can be used for validation of development scenarios across industries and within diverse applications (Aizstrauts and Gunters, 2024).

The ECE's multi-layer architecture and functionality is discussed below.

3.2. Structure of multi-layer Easy Communication Environment

ECE is a versatile communication tool that is accessible to modellers. It's primary goal is to facilitate communication between diverse simulation models. Additionally, it aims to be user-friendly for distributed simulation model designers, including those with limited software engineering knowledge.

Easy Communication Environment's structural multi-layer model has an open system architecture based on the basic building principles of OSI ISO 7498 (ISO/IEC 7498-1:1994(E), 2024; Ginters et al., 2011) and Dijkstra machines (Dijkstra, 1968). However, the Zimmerman's

1980 definition of open systems serves as the foundation for the concept (Zimmermann, 1980).

The ECE structural model (1) (see Figure 2) consists of four layers, each of which is responsible for specific functional tasks – ECE framework messaging protocol (A), ECE framework notation (B), ECE framework messaging library (C) and Simulation sub-model (D) (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Figure 2. ECE structural model.

ECE framework is determined by:

$$ECE = \langle A, B, C, D \rangle \quad (1)$$

where A, B, C and D – functional layers.

ECE layer stack can be described as an open virtual machine's set

$$ECE = \bigcup_{j=1}^J OVM_j \quad (2)$$

where J – number of virtual machines in ECE environment.

And each virtual machine is

$$OVM_j = \langle A_j, B_j, C_j, D_j \rangle \quad (3)$$

where A_j, B_j, C_j, D_j is the layer that provides service for the corresponding j -virtual machine.

The functionality of an open virtual machine can be described using causal loop diagram (CLD) (See Figure 3).

According the CLD diagram, each layer provides a service to the adjacent layer.

Figure 3 shows the interaction of distributed simulation models (stored on one or several virtual machines OVM_j) in the D-layer.

Figure 4, in turn, shows two virtual machines OVM_j and OVM_{j+l} . Both are the foundational elements of ECE environment. Each virtual machine contains a set of distributed simulation models *Sub – models* D_j and *Sub – models* D_{j+l} .

Figure 3. Causal loop diagram of open ECE OVM_j layer interaction.

Figure 4. Interaction of simulation model sets.

Each D_j can host any of the following simulation model sets:

- Separate and independent models, that do not communicate with other simulation models and therefore do not use ECE services.
- Homogeneous and distributed models, that function on a single virtual machine and their interaction is ensured by built-in communication mechanism. The usage of ECE is optional.
- Heterogeneous models that are deployed in one or more virtual machines and ECE is the only possible communication mechanism.

The main task of each ECE j -layer is to provide a service function S to the adjacent layer, by processing consecutive layer's output O dataset. ECE transmission mechanism is described as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} I_{A_{j+l}} = S_{B_{j+l}}^{A_{j+l}}(O_{B_{j+l}}) \\ I_{B_{j+l}} = S_{C_{j+l}}^{B_{j+l}}(O_{C_{j+l}}) \\ I_{C_{j+l}} = S_{D_{j+l}}^{C_{j+l}}(O_{D_{j+l}}) \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

where $I_{C_{j+l}}$ – layer C_{j+l} input, $O_{D_{j+l}}$ – layer D_{j+l} output, but $S_{D_{j+l}}^{C_{j+l}}$ – layer C_{j+l} service function for layer D_{j+l} (access to corresponding simulation suit ECE libraries),

un $I_{B_{j+l}}$ – layer B_{j+l} input, $O_{C_{j+l}}$ – layer C_{j+l} output, but $S_{C_{j+l}}^{B_{j+l}}$ – layer B_{j+l} service function for layer C_{j+l} (access to data notation transformation),

bet $I_{A_{j+l}}$ – layer A_{j+l} input, $O_{B_{j+l}}$ – layer B_{j+l} output, but $S_{B_{j+l}}^{A_{j+l}}$ – layer A_{j+l} service function for layer B_{j+l} (access to data transportation).

Limitations. Unlike OSI ISO 7498, ECE does not ensure direct communication of different virtual machines within the same layer. That is, C_j and C_{j+l} are unable to communicate without services provided by other layers. It is possible only with a set of links E .

Model communication is described by set of links E . ECE can provide communication between simulation models within one virtual machine (for example, $E_{D_j}^k$ and $E_{D_j}^{k+1}$), as well as communication among models *Sub – models* D_j and *Sub – models* D_{j+l} across multiple virtual machines ($E_{D_j}^{k+2}$ and $E_{D_{j+l}}^{m+1}$).

That means that communication among distributed and heterogeneous models D_j^{k+2} and D_{j+l}^{m+1} that are deployed on different virtual machines OVM_j and OVM_{j+l} , is provided by a chain of services $E_{D_j}^{k+2}$:

$$E_{D_j}^{k+2} = \{D_j^{k+2}, S_{D_j}^C, S_{C_j}^B, S_{B_j}^A, S_{B_{j+l}}^{A_{j+l}}, S_{C_{j+l}}^{B_{j+l}}, S_{D_{j+l}}^C, D_{j+l}^{m+1}\} \quad (5)$$

The functional description of each layer A, B, C or D from the service chain are as follows.

A – layer: *ECE framework messaging protocol.* Messaging protocol consists of two functional parts – message transportation and message carrier format.

For message transportation ECE uses Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) protocol. It is an open standard application layer protocol for message-oriented middleware. The defining features of AMQP are message orientation, queuing, routing (including point-to-point and publish-and-subscribe) and reliability (Naik, 2017). Reliability is one of the core features of AMQP, and it offers two preliminary levels of Quality of Service (QoS) for delivery of messages – “At most once” and “At least once” (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

ECE uses “At most once” service level, the recipient does not acknowledge receipt of the message. Data storage functionality is implemented at ECE architecture abstraction layer C. For the message carrier ECE uses JSON data format.

ECE combines AMQP and JSON to deliver sophisticated communication architecture that is highly reliable and easy maintainable. AMQP ensures that message is delivered to the right client/subscriber (and resilience) and JSON allows to transmit complicated data that can be parsed and understood by most of the programming languages.

B – layer: *ECE framework messaging notation.* This layer ensures that each node (sub-model) under-stands each other and speaks the same language. ECE notation is based on JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) data format and requires three fields for the message (see. Table 1).

Table 1. ECE inter layer messaging format (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Field	Description
<i>tick</i>	Simulation modelling time, when the message has been sent.
<i>datatype</i>	Describes what type of data has been sent.
<i>data</i>	The data to be sent to other simulation models.

C – layer: *ECE framework messaging library*. Messaging library is a custom built software that integrates into modelling toolkit, simulation suits, etc. as extensions or plugins. The abstraction layers of the ECE architecture are generic and open, and it is possible to independently develop such extensions/plugins for different simulation tools.

The ECE messaging library (C-layer) includes the basic functions that enable interoperability with the D-layer (see Table 2).

Table 2. ECE messaging library (C-layer) (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Function	Description
<i>init</i>	Initialises the connection to AMQP server.
<i>close</i>	Closes the connection to AMQP server.
<i>isConnected</i>	Returns the status of the connection to AMQP server.
<i>Subscribe</i>	Subscribes to communication topic. Will receive and store all messages that are sent to that topic.
<i>Unsubscribe</i>	Unsubscribes from topic, will not receive any messages to this topic and purges all messages that were received before.
<i>sendString</i>	Sends String type message to specific topic.
<i>sendInteger</i>	Sends Integer type message to specific topic.
<i>sendDouble</i>	Sends Double type message to specific topic.
<i>sendBoolean</i>	Sends Boolean type message to specific topic.
<i>getStringData</i>	Returns String data for specific topic at specific tick.
<i>getIntegerData</i>	Returns Integer data for specific topic at specific tick.
<i>getDoubleData</i>	Returns Double data for specific topic at specific tick.
<i>getBooleanData</i>	Returns Boolean data for specific topic at specific tick.
<i>getLastStringData</i>	Returns String data for specific topic with the latest (largest) tick.
<i>getLastIntegerData</i>	Returns Integer data for specific topic with the latest (largest) tick.
<i>getLastDoubleData</i>	Returns Double data for specific topic with the latest (largest) tick.
<i>getLastBooleanData</i>	Returns Boolean data for specific topic with the latest (largest) tick.
<i>getLastTick</i>	Returns the latest (largest) tick for specific topic.

D – layer: *Simulation sub-model.* Sub-model is any program or algorithm that consumes or produces any data. Such sub-model uses API of extensions/plugin from C-layer to send or receive data from other models. To ensure mutual interoperability of two or more simulation models (D-layer) and data exchange during the session, a chain of cooperation (E) between ECE layers is established (see Figure 4).

The next chapter explains ECE communication algorithm in more detail.

3.3. Functionality description

The interoperability of the ECE A, B, C and D-layers is shown in the BPMN2 diagram (see Annex A). Diagram shows the collaboration between the two simulation models (D-layer). The processes occurring in each layer during the simulation session are parallel. Parallel processes exchange messages and signals, and a process that occurs in one layer can initiate and/or affect another process in the other layer (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

The ECE initialization operation is activated at the D-layer "Simulation sub-model" by sending a signal to the C-layer "ECE framework messaging library". If the model wants to send data, then the appropriate command of the library in the C-layer is called. If the model does not have any data to transmit, and the simulation session is over, then a signal is sent that stops the plug-in of the model in the C-layer.

C-layer processes are activated by a signal that is received from the D-layer simulation model. Upon receiving a signal about the launch of the simulation session, the C-layer provides a connection to the AMQP server. If a data message is received from the D-layer, then a raw data object is created from it, which is transferred to the B-layer "ECE framework notation". Receiving a data object activates the B-layer, where the message is transformed in the JSON data format, and then the message is sent back to the C-layer. After that the message in JSON format is sent to the AMQP server on the A-layer "ECE framework messaging protocol". If the C-layer has not received a signal about the end of the simulation session, then the process of sending data continues, otherwise the connection to the AMQP server is interrupted. The A-layer is activated by data message received from the C-layer. The message is recorded to an AMQP storage queue corresponding to a specific data topic. At the same time, the AMQP server broadcasts a queued data message.

The sent message will then go to the model that needs it and who has subscribed to it. In the C-layer of the other simulation model, the received AMQP message is converted to internal

raw format and recognized, but then converted to JSON format again in B-layer and sent back to C-layer, where the message is stored in topic local storage. If the process is not interrupted by a signal received from the D-layer about the end of the simulation session, then it is divided in two directions - a request to read data from the D-layer is pending and a signal to subscribe to topic is expected at the same time. The data object in the internal format is then sent to the simulation model (D-layer), while the message in JSON format goes to the queues in the A-layer, which correspond to the relevant topic and are deployed in the AMQP storage

In the following section, an example of the use of ECE will be described – a fragment from the Skopje bicycle route planning simulator. To demonstrate the operation of ECE, this model has a user interface that was not available in original the Skopje model.

3.4. Results and discussion

ECE use-case: a fraction of Skopje VeloRouter simulation, that was developed within FUPOL project and that utilises ECE. It is not the full model of Skopje network simulation, but its sub-network, which is aimed to show the use of the ECE. The task of the distributed and heterogenous model is to simulate the occupancy in different segments of the route, so that the cyclist can combine the most suitable route.

The model concept map (see Figure 5) includes simulator objects that provide the necessary functionality. Segments occupancy simulation is provided by RePast agent-based model. Weather data is coming from the Python model, while simulator control and information visualization are implemented in the NetLogo environment.

All simulator sub-models are connected to the ECE, which provides communication and data exchange options. Each model specification (D-layer) includes commands that ensure that notifications/data are sent and received (subscribe/send/get).

The task of the modeler is to embed the appropriate commands in the model specification. ECE parts A, B and C are not the subject of interest to the modeler.

Figure 5. Simulator concept map.

Causal loop diagram (CLD) (see Figure 6) describes the concept of simulator functionality.

Figure 6. Causal loop diagram of route planning.

The simulator helps to the cyclist in selecting right segments of travel route. The selection of segment is influenced by meteorological conditions, which can impair the quality of the path surface. On the other hand, in bad weather, the occupancy on routes decreases due to a decrease in the number of cyclists. Route load is affected by the season (winter, summer) and calendar (weekdays and holidays), during which the number of cyclists increases/decreases. The occupancy affects the choice of a particular route segment, since the profiles of the cyclist are different and determined by the set of attributes: skills, type of bike, age, presence of children in the group, size of the group, etc. Each selection increases the number of cyclists on the segment, which in turn leads to an increase in occupancy. The increase in occupancy reduces the probability of route selection in further iterations. The initial conditions of the simulation session are adjusted with real occupancy data creating a balanced system.

Simulation control (see Figure 7) is implemented in NetLogo and ensures control and visualization options. The user interface has three compartments – Control, Map visualization

and Results. (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Setup button initializes model and ECE communication, that is, defines global variables and subscribe for ECE session. In this case all the global values will be received from other models via ECE. Then ECE NetLogo plugin instance (C-layer) will asynchronously receive data for each of subscribed topics and store it locally with specific timestamp (tick from the message itself) (see Figure 8).

The C-layer libraries at the beginning of the simulation session must connect to ECE AMQP server. It is done with commands *ece:init*, in this case connection is to *localhost*.

Go button starts and stops simulation process. Starting time and selected travel date are manually adjustable. Time is defined as minute of 24 hours, but date is consecutive day of year.

Figure 7. Simulation model control view (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

User can define parameters for the bicycle lane surface and surrounding infrastructure using dropdown menus $ROAD_i$. The user simulates the occupancy within six different route edges with this model. The map shows four starting points/destinations (vertices P1, P2, P3 and P4),

bicycle lanes among these points are split into six edges (a, b, c, d, e and f). Lane/road usage is simulated for each edge separately using RePast.

```

extensions [ece]
globals[
  last_temperature
  last_wind
  last_precipitation
  new_cyclist_data
  last_new_cyclist_data_tick
]

to setup_ece
  ece:init "localhost"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_temp"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_wind"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_precip"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_new_cyclist_agent"
end

```

Figure 8. NetLogo Setup implementation.

NetLogo model source code (D-layer) contains calls to C-layer library functions (see Figure 9).

```

extensions [ece]
globals[last_temperature last_wind last_precipitation new_cyclist_data last_new_cyclist_data_tick]

to setup_ece
  ece:init "localhost"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_temp"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_wind"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_precip"
  ece:subscribe "FUPOL_SIMULATION_new_cyclist_agent"
end

to send_time_and_date
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_time" ticks MinuteOfTheDay
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_date" ticks DayOfTheYear
end

to send_road_configuration
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_a" ticks ROAD_a
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_b" ticks ROAD_b
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_c" ticks ROAD_c
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_d" ticks ROAD_d
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_e" ticks ROAD_e
  ece:sendNumber "FUPOL_SIMULATION_road_f" ticks ROAD_f
end

to get_last_weather_data
  set last_temperature ece:getLastNumberData "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_temp"
  set last_wind ece:getLastNumberData "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_wind"
  set last_precipitation ece:getLastNumberData "FUPOL_SIMULATION_weather_precip"
end

to get_new_cyclist_data
  if last_new_cyclist_data_tick != ece:getLastTick("FUPOL_SIMULATION_new_cyclist_agent") [
    set new_cyclist_data ece:getLastStringData("FUPOL_SIMULATION_new_cyclist_agent")
    set last_new_cyclist_data_tick ece:getLastTick("FUPOL_SIMULATION_new_cyclist_agent")
  ]
end

```

Figure 9. NetLogo model D-layer specification. (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Results panel shows potential weather conditions for the chosen date and time (precipitation, wind speed and temperature) generated by Python and a bar chart with expected occupancy for each simulated edge. According to the occupancy results, the cyclist can decide

to include this segment in his route or not.

Since the weather simulation is carried out using Python, ECE library (C-layer) extends Python model (D-layer) functionality with capabilities to communicate via ECE. The main task of this model is to transmit the possible weather conditions for the particular date.

This occupancy simulation model is created in the Repast Symphony environment using ECE for communication with other simulation models according to previously validated algorithm (Ginters, Aizstrauts et al., 2016). RePast C-layer is designed in generic pattern and can be implemented in any Java application.

In this example, the modeler has to include in ECE C-layer defined commands into ECE D-layers sub model, and higher ECE layers will provide communication services (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

Discussion. If the modeler possesses the necessary skillset to prepare NetLogo, RePast, or other simulation model code, he will be able to incorporate the required ECE commands. The level of complexity is not even comparable to those software engineering skills required for HLA use.

The performance of the distributed model is determined by the model's interoperability algorithm designed by the modeler, while ECE provides only the communication means. The same can be said for HLA. The exciting question would be, which of the communication environments HLA or ECE has higher performance?

Since security rather than maximal throughput is HLA's main tenet, real-time applications hardly use HLA. HLA ensures acknowledgement (approval) functionality, and that is included in every federation. That increases security, but also impacts computing time and causes delays in communication. ECE transmission mechanism is lighter and therefore faster. ECE is based on AMQP protocol and communication delays are less than using HLA. ECE saves time on message processing by not requiring message acknowledgement. AMQP is also significantly faster than HTTP (*Hypertext Transfer Protocol*), and if modeler deploys the simulation models geographically distributed, ECE will not cause communication delays (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024)

Is AMQP fast enough for real-time applications when a modeler creates digital twins for real-time control of IoT objects?

IoT applications usually use more primitive protocols, such as Message Queue Telemetry

Transport (MQTT), because shorter data messages are used to control the technical system. The usage of ECE for designing heterogeneous systems would be severely constrained if it were to be built on the MQTT protocol. However, the RabbitMQ stack also includes MQTT, so customizing ECE wouldn't be a problem.

ECE provides the modeler with reasonable communication latency, scalability, modularity, security, and performance. However, if the modeler requires distributed simulation models for digital twins for critical infrastructure control or life-saving services, it is advisable to use industry-recognized HLA and involve highly qualified software engineers starting from the initial development steps.

Still, attempts to make HLA more accessible and replace it with Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) in critical simulation applications have failed (Iagaru, 2022).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The sociotechnical systems that permeate our society and industry are complex due to their dependence on numerous stochastic factors, of which the most significant, but also the least predictable is human behaviour. It is particularly difficult to model the behaviour of several individual objects and their interaction. Simulation modelling can be used to examine various scenarios and possible outcomes of our actions. Homogeneous simulation models are unable to accurately represent complex processes and phenomena, therefore distributed and heterogeneous simulation models are used. However, that causes one major challenge – to ensure data exchange between these models and coordinating their communication during a modelling session.

Surprising as it may seem, the designers of distributed simulation models still rely on HLA environment, which is not accessible to modelers without specific knowledge and software engineering skills (Aizstrauts and Ginters, 2024).

That hinders adequate policy decision-making and scenario analysis across domains, as modelling becomes dependent on specific skillset. Working with the HLA environment necessitates the involvement of highly skilled software engineers. Due to this problem, modelling is hardly useful as a tool for assessing actions and their results, particularly in non-technical organisations like NGOs, municipalities, or other governing bodies.

There is still a second option: to use one of the multifunctional but closed simulation environments and hope that this environment will be sustainable and versatile and has a long enough life cycle.

Over 17 years, the author has developed and validated the ECE data exchange environment for distributed and heterogeneous simulation, which is accessible to professionals in other industries without specific software engineering skills.

A stack of flexible protocols and data formats have been used in ECE design, the changes of which do not cause problems in running simulation models.

Multi-layer open architecture provides interoperability of various simulation technologies.

The advantages of ECE are its application not only in the development of distributed simulation models, but also in the provision of software subsystems interoperability, so ECE audience is not only researchers and modelers, but also developers of distributed data processing systems.

The concept and functionality of the ECE have been validated in several national and European Commission funded projects, while research results have been published in various sources and announced at international conferences.

To conclude, the objectives of the doctoral thesis have been met as well as it's main aim to allow modelers lacking programming engineering background to create distributed and heterogeneous simulation models, based on conceptual framework of open and easy communication environment. The results of the doctoral thesis support the proposed statements.

For the time being, ECE lacks sufficient methodological and training materials, and the number of libraries of simulation tools is still limited. However, the author intends to continue to work on the preparation of these deliverables.

The next step of ECE is to connect heterogeneous simulation models to a Bayesian network to enable cyber threat forecasting for individual nodes of data transmission network.

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A. ANNEX. EASY COMMUNICATION ENVIRONMENT (ECE) FUNCTIONALITY AS A BPMN2 DIAGRAM

BPMN2 diagram of ECE functionality to send data.

BPMN2 diagram of ECE functionality to receive data.

